

Conductances of alkali metal chlorides and bromides in aqueous binary mixture of 2-methoxyethanol at 298.15 K

Debasis Nandi and Dilip K. Hazra*

Department of Chemistry, North Bengal University, Darjeeling-734 430, India

Fax : 91-0353-581546

Manuscript received 19 August 2002, accepted 12 September 2002

Precise conductance measurements are reported for alkali metal chlorides and bromides in 2-methoxyethanol (ME) + water mixture ($69.73 \geq \epsilon \leq 19.01$) at 298.15 K in the concentration range $0.001\text{--}0.08 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$. The limiting molar conductivity (Λ_0), the association constant (K_A) and the association distance (R) in the solvent mixtures have been evaluated using the Fuoss conductance equation. The single ionic conductances have been evaluated using conductance data for the reference electrolyte Bu_4NBPh_4 . The analysis of our data indicates that the electrolytes are poorly associated in 20, 30 and 40 wt% of ME, whereas in 60, 80, and 90 wt% of ME association is strong. The variation of ionic Walden products with the solvent compositions have been determined and discussed. The limiting ionic conductance ($\Lambda_0^\pm$) values for alkali metal ions flow the order : $\text{Li}^+ < \text{Na}^+ < \text{K}^+ < \text{Rb}^+ < \text{Cs}^+$, and for anions : $\text{Br}^- < \text{Cl}^-$. The results have been explained in terms of ion-solvent interactions and structural changes in the mixed solvents.

2-Methoxyethanol (ME) – commonly known as methyl cellosolve – has drawn much attention as a solvent medium for various electrochemical investigations and industrial processes^{1,2}. ME is an amphiprotic dipolar solvent of low dielectric constant ($\epsilon = 16.93$, at 298.15 K). It has unique solvating properties associated with large dipole moment ($\mu = 2.36 \text{ D}$)³ with its quasiaprotic character⁴ and is a probable solvent for anions through its hydrogen-bonding network and dipole-induced interaction. As it is a monomethyl ether of ethyleneglycol, it is very likely to show physicochemical properties midway between protic and aprotic solvents.

We have previously reported¹ the conductances of alkali metal halides in 2-methoxyethanol at 298.15 K. In the present paper we report the conductances of alkali metal ($\text{M}^+ = \text{Li}, \text{Na}, \text{K}, \text{Rb}$ and Cs) chlorides and bromides in aqueous binary mixture of 2-methoxyethanol (ME) to understand the nature of ion-solvent interactions in this non-aqueous solvent.

Results and discussion

The mixed solvents of ME with water were prepared by weight. Solvent properties of ME-water mixtures are given in Table 1. The measured conductances and the corresponding molarities for alkali metal salts in ME-water mixtures are given in Table 2.

The data were analyzed by the Fuoss conductance equation⁶ using the following set of equations :

$$\Lambda = P[\Lambda_0(1 + \Delta\kappa/x + \Delta\Lambda_c)] \quad (1)$$

$$P = [1 - \alpha(1 - \nu)] \quad (2)$$

$$n = 1 - K_A C \nu^2 f^2 \quad (3)$$

$$-\ln f = \beta \kappa / 2(1 + \kappa R) \quad (4)$$

$$\beta = e^2 / \epsilon k T \quad (5)$$

$$K_A = (1 - \nu) / C \nu^2 f^2 \quad (6)$$

where $\Delta\kappa/x$ and Λ_c are relaxation and hydrodynamic terms which are complicated functions of Λ_0 and the distance parameter R and the other terms have their usual meaning⁶. The parameters Λ_0 , K_A and R are obtained from the above equations by finding the values of Λ_0 and ν which minimize

$$\sigma^2 = [\Lambda_{j(\text{cal})} - \Lambda_{j(\text{obs})}]^2 / (n - 2) \quad (7)$$

for a sequence of R values. Here, n is the number of data points. From a plot of $\sigma\% = 100 \sigma / \Lambda_0$ against R , the best fit R corresponds to the minimum in the curve. Initial Λ_0 value for the iteration procedure was taken from Shedlovsky

Table 1. Dielectric constant (ϵ), density (ρ) and viscosity (η) of 2-methoxyethanol (ME)-water mixtures at 298.15 K

Wt% ME	X_2	ϵ^a	ρ g cm ⁻³	$10^2 \eta$ cP
0	0	78.54	0.99707	0.8903
20	0.056	69.73	1.00240	1.5165
30	0.092	64.10	1.00657	1.9465
40	0.136	57.41	1.00690	2.3655
60	0.262	42.11	1.00233	2.8849
80	0.486	26.53	0.98572	2.5751
90	0.680	19.01	0.97570	2.1342
100	1.000	16.93	0.96002	1.5414

^aTaken from Ref. 5.

Table 2. Conductance data of alkali metal chlorides and bromides in 2-methoxyethanol-water mixtures at 298.15 K

$10^4 C$ mol dm ⁻³	Λ S cm ² mol ⁻¹	$10C$ mol dm ⁻³	Λ S cm ² mol ⁻¹	$10C$ mol dm ⁻³	Λ S cm ² mol ⁻¹	$10C$ mol dm ⁻³	Λ S cm ² mol ⁻¹
Lithium chloride							
$X_2 = 0.056$		$X_2 = 0.136$		$X_2 = 0.262$		$X_2 = 0.486$	
750.281	57.08	414.234	38.60	161.360	27.69	52.136	25.18
653.282	58.04	372.253	39.06	130.027	28.21	37.592	25.68
523.871	59.73	321.857	39.66	104.910	28.80	33.028	26.12
410.239	61.24	271.641	40.32	87.194	29.26	28.726	26.35
357.391	62.06	235.210	40.86	75.623	29.46	24.524	26.58
289.645	63.19	198.779	41.44	53.928	30.07	20.398	26.84
244.165	63.96	110.289	43.04	43.525	30.41	13.597	27.28
204.758	64.73	92.319	43.50	33.353	30.76	9.738	27.65
139.249	66.21						
Sodium chloride							
717.904	67.04	415.622	41.64	160.982	31.18	51.791	26.47
669.867	67.01	382.597	42.14	132.185	31.76	37.238	27.14
540.124	69.02	347.396	42.69	103.678	32.38	30.197	27.53
410.231	70.66	309.189	43.44	92.343	32.65	24.781	27.92
299.989	72.25	265.531	44.30	71.117	33.17	19.357	28.25
264.647	72.80	175.021	46.26	52.283	33.77	17.438	28.40
230.493	73.38	134.571	47.24	41.164	34.17	14.117	28.70
202.834	73.86	97.293	48.35	32.216	34.46	9.356	29.08
160.215	74.74						
Potassium chloride							
701.213	78.05	414.129	50.25	161.021	35.60	51.449	29.71
676.510	78.34	372.576	50.80	135.008	36.20	41.001	30.27
524.389	80.67	337.189	51.38	107.261	36.84	36.892	30.50
478.668	81.27	311.209	51.70	94.683	37.15	31.897	30.83
349.821	83.67	281.281	52.24	74.895	37.73	28.956	31.08
299.643	84.71	246.081	52.77	54.926	38.37	20.769	31.90
223.970	86.24	169.239	54.21	46.334	38.74	14.831	32.27
182.817	87.35	98.126	55.99	34.013	39.20	9.213	32.74
Rubidium chloride							
345.192	83.02	413.987	52.45	161.091	36.02	54.122	30.21
298.598	84.04	368.194	53.01	125.899	36.84	44.294	30.73
256.889	85.11	315.299	53.75	101.585	37.43	37.296	31.13
198.721	86.64	275.312	54.09	83.836	37.95	32.983	31.45
171.714	87.44	227.837	55.02	61.155	38.87	27.591	31.75
143.405	88.37	169.312	56.06	49.694	39.15	21.029	32.38
101.120	89.96	134.339	56.77	38.466	39.60	15.036	32.93
92.839	90.25	90.128	57.80	25.436	40.21	9.789	33.41
Cesium chloride							
352.920	82.22	412.893	51.49	161.046	36.22	46.298	30.52
301.280	83.64	363.832	52.21	119.191	37.25	37.523	31.16
225.829	85.86	312.313	53.00	93.025	37.82	31.549	31.73
189.211	87.18	273.861	53.70	72.351	38.56	28.183	32.06
151.388	88.54	221.894	54.64	59.827	39.00	23.186	32.57
121.021	89.77	165.316	55.84	48.596	39.44	17.391	33.67
95.892	90.98	130.691	56.75	37.378	39.97	13.265	33.74
83.451	91.64	97.882	57.69	26.285	40.51	9.329	34.48
Lithium bromide							
$X_2 = 0.056$		$X_2 = 0.092$		$X_2 = 0.136$		$X_2 = 0.262$	
631.249	48.29	772.451	41.89	410.208	27.33	158.116	23.34
525.326	49.16	689.359	42.55	369.854	27.95	125.495	24.04
413.295	49.99	467.692	44.45	328.073	28.56	95.239	24.80
293.567	51.14	325.819	46.01	279.698	29.45	75.621	25.42
256.898	51.56	265.488	46.77	231.106	30.34	63.528	25.73
197.985	52.33	193.630	47.77	174.303	31.59	51.827	26.03
145.892	53.06	92.380	49.67	127.784	32.74	39.289	26.49
				92.198	33.73	27.232	27.06

$X_2 = 0.486$		$X_2 = 0.680$					
52.471	22.28	131.294	21.15				
44.484	22.85	103.693	21.58				
36.928	23.46	84.265	22.04				
31.689	23.83	68.489	22.43				
25.525	24.32	42.019	23.19				
20.729	24.75	24.237	23.87				
15.660	25.36	13.671	24.35				
11.862	25.81						
$X_2 = 0.056$		$X_2 = 0.092$		$X_2 = 0.136$		$X_2 = 0.262$	
708.938	64.82	772.390	51.91	418.773	43.35	129.276	31.07
632.989	65.54	689.291	52.37	369.622	43.86	113.289	31.49
568.943	66.04	467.619	53.60	315.559	44.48	99.236	31.97
497.894	66.80	325.790	54.60	256.576	45.19	88.539	32.24
358.976	68.40	193.609	55.82	196.453	46.01	76.355	32.71
276.892	69.32	91.171	56.98	157.813	46.74	52.351	33.59
231.598	70.02			119.558	47.52	39.254	34.14
161.287	71.34			97.839	47.95	28.029	34.79
$X_2 = 0.486$		$X_2 = 0.680$					
48.966	28.16	135.211	23.33				
42.896	28.58	113.679	23.87				
37.295	28.89	96.763	24.35				
31.028	29.42	65.397	25.38				
26.589	29.78	41.962	26.25				
18.925	30.48	26.585	26.98				
13.108	31.08	20.969	27.36				
10.499	31.42	13.510	27.84				
$X_2 = 0.056$		$X_2 = 0.092$		$X_2 = 0.136$		$X_2 = 0.262$	
767.498	76.60	759.827	61.55	416.731	50.48	161.121	35.70
701.870	77.16	689.120	61.93	373.880	50.98	125.686	36.64
678.925	78.24	467.001	63.58	308.887	51.74	110.872	37.16
527.831	78.91	325.820	64.80	251.614	52.62	95.257	37.61
463.852	79.57	193.591	66.22	207.876	53.01	79.218	38.10
338.967	81.01	93.211	67.74	163.737	53.76	67.023	38.55
225.937	82.61			129.463	54.40	43.281	39.59
185.937	83.28			99.440	54.95	29.077	40.34
$X_2 = 0.486$		$X_2 = 0.680$					
54.763	30.36	130.798	26.17				
47.914	30.82	112.347	26.75				
41.222	31.08	93.845	27.35				
33.021	31.66	73.256	28.01				
24.731	32.25	51.784	28.76				
16.858	32.83	36.494	29.73				
13.310	33.18	13.101	31.31				
10.837	33.45						
$X_2 = 0.056$		$X_2 = 0.092$		$X_2 = 0.136$		$X_2 = 0.262$	
471.072	79.88	676.414	61.80	412.747	50.57	168.439	36.40
422.623	80.55	586.983	62.18	364.664	51.34	133.052	37.02
360.718	81.54	466.981	64.11	316.071	51.84	115.23	37.68
266.020	83.18	398.431	65.26	248.018	52.85	99.238	38.04
231.376	83.78	280.151	66.24	205.176	53.55	85.771	38.44
192.023	84.65	201.340	67.20	170.203	54.22	74.685	38.77
168.928	85.20	136.171	68.04	135.560	54.96	63.722	39.16
147.851	85.81	93.159	68.95	96.983	55.84	40.927	40.00
$X_2 = 0.486$		$X_2 = 0.680$					
50.397	31.18	132.693	26.43				
43.831	31.60	110.984	27.20				
38.021	31.96	94.316	27.83				
33.218	32.28	69.934	28.85				
25.256	32.74	46.396	30.00				
18.031	33.42	29.945	31.01				
13.538	33.90	13.196	32.45				
10.105	34.30						

Cesium bromide							
$X_2 = 0.056$		$X_2 = 0.092$		$X_2 = 0.136$		$X_2 = 0.262$	
637.371	77.53	744.594	62.24	384.409	50.00	160.071	36.77
580.518	78.37	688.370	62.61	328.921	50.86	140.029	37.22
514.297	79.30	467.131	64.38	272.072	51.86	121.351	37.60
499.321	80.20	325.690	65.77	220.302	52.84	106.279	37.93
344.184	81.86	194.121	67.24	178.281	53.75	94.825	38.18
265.660	83.33	94.191	69.12	139.476	54.64	81.021	38.46
200.024	84.66			108.672	55.36	41.927	39.64
111.823	86.97			92.991	55.95		
$X_2 = 0.486$		$X_2 = 0.680$					
51.867	32.34	134.137	26.77				
45.469	32.61	108.673	27.84				
38.805	32.92	85.967	29.08				
28.182	33.50	63.413	30.65				
23.126	33.80	41.908	32.25				
17.392	34.21	30.092	33.33				
11.827	34.62	13.396	35.35				
9.325	34.89						
Sodium tetraphenylborate							
$X_2 = 0.056$		$X_2 = 0.092$		$X_2 = 0.136$		$X_2 = 0.262$	
800.002	36.25	622.497	29.57	800.001	24.21	400.001	21.04
699.985	36.86	528.370	29.90	559.992	24.37	311.621	21.94
499.999	41.00	416.950	30.27	399.995	25.98	249.997	22.58
220.002	41.50	306.031	30.80	201.002	27.25	151.252	23.87
99.999	42.51	173.962	31.56	99.999	28.40	79.996	25.11
59.898	43.58	94.053	32.17	59.985	28.85	60.001	25.49
49.002	44.50			49.899	29.01	39.997	25.99
29.989	45.62			29.997	29.50	20.003	26.71
$X_2 = 0.486$		$X_2 = 0.680$					
50.001	18.72	131.94	18.15				
39.999	19.60	103.869	18.64				
19.997	21.25	79.473	19.13				
9.985	22.40	53.801	19.77				
8.007	22.91	36.497	22.28				
4.999	23.44	23.194	20.73				
3.002	24.01	12.971	21.15				
Tetrabutylammonium bromide							
$X_2 = 0.056$		$X_2 = 0.092$		$X_2 = 0.136$		$X_2 = 0.262$	
801.001	42.37	556.231	33.56	799.987	24.07	399.998	22.50
700.021	43.14	444.679	35.53	599.879	29.02	249.905	27.51
499.997	45.60	385.932	36.68	401.002	31.60	150.001	32.07
99.999	54.51	313.409	38.25	200.011	36.50	80.011	36.52
60.033	55.67	232.978	40.18	99.997	40.51	59.999	38.50
39.997	57.00	158.360	42.27	79.898	41.25	40.011	39.49
29.989	57.51	95.950	44.45	50.007	43.00	20.012	42.55
		32.417	47.69	29.997	45.01		
$X_2 = 0.486$		$X_2 = 0.680$					
49.999	23.54	132.463	19.55				
40.011	24.53	104.795	20.15				
19.999	27.00	82.316	20.74				
9.997	28.82	65.294	21.16				
7.999	29.25	48.347	21.68				
4.967	30.01	34.627	22.23				
2.998	30.75	21.395	22.81				

extrapolations of the data. The values of Λ_0 , K_A and R obtained by this procedure are recorded in Table 3. The values of Λ_0 for alkali metal halides generally increase as the size of the cation increases for each mole fraction of mixed solvent. This is in agreement with earlier findings in several pure and mixed hydrogen bonding solvents⁷ and

can be attributed to the size and structure-breaking effect of the cations⁸.

However, for any particular electrolyte, Λ_0 continuously decreases with the addition of ME, passes through a minimum around 0.486 mole fraction of ME and then increases again. Further, Λ_0 for the alkali metal chlorides are greater

Table 3. Derived conductance parameters

X_2	Λ_0 $S\text{ cm}^2\text{ mol}^{-1}$	K_A $\text{dm}^3\text{ mol}^{-1}$	R $\text{\AA}$	$\Lambda_0\eta_0$	σ
Lithium chloride					
0	115.05 ± 0.01	0.89	5.19	1.02	0.03
0.056	62.52 ± 0.05	3.9 ± 0.1	9.40	0.95	0.04
0.136	47.97 ± 0.02	5.8 ± 0.1	10.00	1.14	0.02
0.262	34.39 ± 0.04	12.1 ± 0.3	15.00	0.99	0.04
0.486	29.73 ± 0.08	32.3 ± 1.8	21.00	0.76	0.07
1.000	39.99 ± 0.47	587.0 ± 42.0	7.50	0.62	0.16
Sodium chloride					
0	126.53 ± 0.01	0.81	5.56	1.13	0.02
0.056	82.20 ± 0.02	2.7 ± 0.1	9.40	1.25	0.02
0.136	53.83 ± 0.04	8.5 ± 0.1	14.00	1.27	0.03
0.262	38.64 ± 0.02	11.4 ± 0.1	14.00	1.12	0.02
0.486	31.21 ± 0.03	32.6 ± 0.7	21.00	0.80	0.03
1.000	35.42 ± 0.23	290.0 ± 31.0	7.85	0.54	0.24
Potassium chloride					
0	149.90 ± 0.01	0.66	4.65	1.33	0.02
0.056	94.34 ± 0.08	3.6 ± 0.1	9.20	1.43	0.06
0.136	60.14 ± 0.04	5.5 ± 0.1	9.01	1.45	0.03
0.262	42.65 ± 0.05	9.7 ± 0.3	6.70	1.23	0.05
0.486	35.03 ± 0.10	35.7 ± 1.8	26.01	0.90	0.09
1.00	40.12 ± 0.48	410.0 ± 13.0	8.22	0.62	0.06
Rubidium chloride					
0	153.64 ± 0.01	0.36	3.35	1.37	0.02
0.056	97.58 ± 0.03	4.3 ± 0.0	8.20	1.48	0.02
0.136	62.51 ± 0.09	4.3 ± 0.1	7.00	1.48	0.08
0.262	42.92 ± 0.06	12.1 ± 0.3	15.00	1.24	0.06
0.486	37.69 ± 0.05	36.6 ± 0.9	19.00	0.97	0.05
1.00	42.98 ± 0.38	462.0 ± 52.0	8.80	0.66	0.21
Cesium chloride					
0	153.04 ± 0.02	0.62	3.62	1.36	0.02
0.056	99.36 ± 0.04	5.8 ± 0.1	8.95	1.51	0.03
0.136	63.57 ± 0.02	6.0 ± 0.1	8.00	1.50	0.02
0.262	43.46 ± 0.02	12.3 ± 0.1	11.00	1.25	0.02
0.486	37.74 ± 0.20	59.7 ± 4.0	24.00	0.97	0.16
1.000	48.13 ± 0.48	9730 ± 63.0	8.30	0.74	0.21
Lithium bromide					
0	116.88			1.04	
0.056	58.65 ± 0.04	2.1 ± 0.01	8.00	0.89	0.03
0.092	53.82 ± 0.06	3.6 ± 0.1	10.00	1.04	0.05
0.136	47.12 ± 0.04	13.2 ± 0.1	17.0	1.12	0.02
0.262	32.51 ± 0.05	17.4 ± 0.4	20.00	0.94	0.05
0.486	29.21 ± 0.10	69.5 ± 2.8	10.60	0.75	0.07
0.680	27.93 ± 0.01	25.2 ± 2.1	11.60	0.59	0.09
1.000	38.22 ± 0.26	328.0 ± 25.0	7.50	0.59	0.05
Sodium bromide					
0	128.42			1.14	
0.056	78.33 ± 0.04	2.2 ± 0.1	7.0	1.19	0.06
0.092	60.90 ± 0.05	1.3 ± 0.1	8.65	1.18	0.05
0.136	52.99 ± 0.04	3.9 ± 0.1	4.90	1.25	0.03
0.262	37.39 ± 0.04	17.3 ± 0.3	13.00	1.09	0.03
0.486	30.70 ± 0.03	48.2 ± 0.6	21.00	0.79	0.02
0.680	31.54 ± 0.07	35.4 ± 1.3	13.00	0.67	0.07
1.000	33.71 ± 0.31	127.0 ± 10.0	7.99	0.52	0.09

Potassium bromide					
0	151.77			1.35	
0.056	90.47±0.35	1.7±0.1	8.00	1.38	0.30
0.092	72.14±0.04	1.6±0.1	8.45	1.40	0.04
0.136	59.30±0.08	3.6±0.1	12.00	1.40	0.06
0.262	40.74±0.19	13.9±0.9	16.00	1.18	0.07
0.486	34.51±0.04	33.8±0.7	22.0	0.89	0.04
0.680	35.24±0.10	40.6±1.5	13.00	0.75	0.07
1.000	38.40±0.10	175.0±8.0	8.34	0.59	0.15
Rubidium bromide					
0	156.37			1.39	
0.056	93.71±0.05	2.6±0.1	6.00	1.42	0.04
0.092	73.22±0.13	2.0±0.1	11.00	1.42	0.15
0.136	61.65±0.07	4.7±0.1	8.00	1.46	0.06
0.262	41.04±0.11	11.9±0.5	15.00	1.18	0.08
0.486	37.17±0.05	31.6±0.9	10.60	0.96	0.04
0.680	36.66±0.07	48.7±1.2	14.00	0.78	0.06
1.000	41.22±0.23	240.0±16.0	8.51	0.63	0.15
Cesium bromide					
0	155.51			1.38	
0.056	95.49±0.05	3.0±0.1	9.00	1.45	0.04
0.092	73.80±0.06	1.9±0.1	7.65	1.43	0.05
0.136	62.72±0.06	6.2±0.8	13.00	1.48	0.05
0.262	42.61±0.03	8.7±0.1	16.00	1.23	0.02
0.486	37.21±0.01	23.6±0.3	19.00	0.96	0.01
0.680	40.60±0.20	81.8±3.3	16.00	0.86	0.13
1.000	46.42±0.27	324.0±34.0	8.69	0.72	0.10
Tetrabutylammonium bromide					
0.056	61.13±0.13	7.0±0.2	7.10	0.93	0.19
0.092	51.06±0.04	13.0±0.1	18.40	0.99	0.05
0.136	49.67±0.26	9.8±0.8	8.50	1.18	0.29
0.262	46.75±0.35	61.7±4.1	17.10	1.35	0.19
0.486	32.88±0.10	105.0±3.9	6.50	0.85	0.12
0.680	26.67±0.06	35.9±1.3	12.20	0.57	0.05
1.000	36.74±0.27	372.0±24.0	11.97	0.57	0.20
Sodium tetraphenylborate					
0.056	44.65±0.48	1.5±0.1	7.50	0.68	0.28
0.092	35.15±0.04	0.7±0.1	9.10	0.68	0.04
0.136	30.77±0.15	3.0±0.3	7.50	0.73	0.24
0.262	28.58±0.02	10.4±0.1	12.20	0.82	0.03
0.486	18.66±0.07	16.0±0.3	13.40	0.48	0.09
0.680	18.97±0.10	17.7±2.4	13.00	0.41	0.12
1.000	24.69±0.13	24.2±0.9	22.70	0.38	0.03

than those for the corresponding alkali metal bromides. Λ_0 in all cases initially decreases with the increase in viscosity of solvated mixtures and the maximum in viscosity does not coincide with the observed minimum in Λ_0 . The results indicate that the hydrodynamic entity is of importance in both cases but the differences in solvation of ions may be responsible for the change in mobility of the ions and hence Λ_0 .

The values of the Walden products for the alkali metal chlorides and bromides pass through a maximum at about 0.136 mole fraction of ME. Similar behavior of the alkali metal halides was observed by Kay and Broadwater in aqueous binary mixture of ethanol⁹ and *t*-butanol¹⁰. Petrella *et al.*¹⁰ also observed similar Walden product maxima for

alkali metal halides in sulfolane-water¹¹, acetonitrile-water¹² and dimethyl sulfoxide-water¹³ mixtures. The existence of this maximum Walden product has been explained by Kay and Broadwater⁹ on the basis of solvent sorting model⁹. Several other significant reasons have also been suggested for this variation, and their mathematical treatments^{14,15} have been given by different workers from time to time. The model proposed by Nakahara and Ibuki¹⁶ demonstrates the influence of residual friction coefficient over the Walden product to explain long-range interactions in the case of smaller ions. In our case, due to the lack of experimental data on intermediate frequency dielectric constants (ϵ_c) and infinite frequency dielectric constants (ϵ_∞) for

Table 4. Values of ionic conductances and Walden products

X_2	λ_0	$\lambda_{0\pm\eta_0}$	X_2	λ_0	$\lambda_{0\pm\eta_0}$
	Lithium			Sodium	
0	38.66	0.34	0	50.14	0.45
0.056	19.22	0.29	0.056	38.97	0.59
0.092	18.68	0.36	0.092	25.76	0.50
0.136	12.02	0.28	0.136	17.88	0.42
0.262	8.20	0.28	0.262	12.45	0.36
0.486	10.61	0.27	0.486	12.09	0.31
0.680	11.31	0.24	0.680	14.92	0.32
1.000	15.95	0.25	1.000	11.44	0.18
	Potassium			Rubidium	
0	73.55	0.66	0	78.15	0.70
0.056	51.11	0.78	0.056	54.35	0.82
0.092	37.00	0.72	0.092	38.08	0.74
0.136	24.19	0.57	0.136	26.59	0.63
0.262	16.43	0.47	0.262	16.73	0.48
0.486	15.90	0.41	0.486	18.57	0.48
0.680	18.62	0.40	0.680	20.04	0.43
1.000	16.08	0.25	1.000	18.94	0.29
	Cesium			Chloride	
0	77.29	0.69	0	76.39	0.68
0.056	56.13	0.85	0.056	43.23	0.66
0.092	38.66	0.75	0.136	35.95	0.85
0.136	27.62	0.65	0.262	26.19	0.76
0.262	15.47	0.45	0.486	19.12	0.49
0.486	18.61	0.48	1.000	24.04	0.37
0.680	23.98	0.51			
1.000	24.10	0.37			
	Bromide			Tetrabutylammonium	
0	78.22	0.70	0	19.31	0.17
0.056	39.36	0.60	0.056	21.77	0.33
0.092	35.14	0.68	0.092	15.92	0.31
0.136	35.10	0.83	0.136	14.57	0.34
0.262	24.31	0.70	0.262	22.44	0.65
0.486	18.60	0.48	0.486	14.28	0.37
0.680	16.66	0.35	0.680	10.05	0.21
1.000	22.27	0.34	1.000	14.47	0.22
	Tetraphenylborate				
0.056	5.68	0.09			
0.092	9.39	0.18			
0.136	12.89	0.30			
0.262	16.13	0.47			
0.486	6.57	0.17			
0.680	4.05	0.09			
1.000	13.25	0.20			

these electrolyte solutions in ME-water mixtures, it would not be possible to follow the method of Nakahara and Ibuki. Alternatively, the Walden product maximum observed in the present study has been explained by Kay's model.

The solvent sorting argument is as follows. In water-ME mixtures, the ion-water interactions are stronger than ion-ME interaction, and therefore in the ionic cosphere there is a higher percentage of water than in the bulk mixture. Due to preferential solvation of these ions by water in this region of the solvent mixtures, viscosity of the solvent in the vicinity of these ions is lower than that of the bulk solvent. Since the bulk viscosity value is used in the calculation of Walden

product, the calculated values of $\Lambda_0\eta_0$ are too high to the point corresponding to the viscosity maximum after which they are low, and therefore a maximum, and since the alkali metal cations have water-rich solvation shells in dilute ME-water mixtures, the observed behavior of these ions is consistent with Kay's model.

From Table 3 we find that association constant (K_A) is very low for all the electrolytes at 0.056, 0.092 and 0.136 mole fraction of ME in ME-H₂O mixtures. This indicates that these salts are not appreciably associated ($K_A < 10$) in these solvent mixtures having high dielectric constant ($69.73 \geq \epsilon \geq 57.47$). We further observe (Table 3) that K_A

values for bromide salts at 0.680 mole fraction of ME in the mixed solvents lie in the sequence, $\text{Li}^+ < \text{Na}^+ < \text{K}^+ < \text{Rb}^+ < \text{Cs}^+$. It is clear that CsBr, in spite of its greater size, is more associated than other bromides at higher percentages of mixed solvents. In general, larger ions are more associated than smaller ions in hydrogen-bonded solvents which has also been observed in the present study.

In absence of accurate transference data in these mixed solvents, we have to use the 'reference electrolyte' method for the division of Λ_o into single-ion values. The $\text{Bu}_4\text{NBPPh}_4$ has been used as the 'reference electrolyte'. The $\Lambda_{o\text{Bu}_4\text{NBPPh}_4}$ has been obtained from the relation¹⁷,

$$\Lambda_{o\text{Bu}_4\text{NBPPh}_4} = \Lambda_{o\text{Bu}_4\text{NBr}} + \Lambda_{o\text{NaBPPh}_4} - \Lambda_{o\text{NaBr}} \quad (8)$$

We have divided Λ_o values of $\text{Bu}_4\text{NBPPh}_4$ using the method similar to that proposed by Krumgalz¹⁸,

$$\frac{\lambda_{o\text{Bu}_4\text{N}^+}}{\lambda_{o\text{Ph}_4\text{B}^-}} = \frac{r_{\text{Ph}_4\text{B}^-}}{r_{\text{Bu}_4\text{N}^+}} = \frac{5.35}{5.00} = 1.07 \quad (9)$$

The r -values have been taken from the works of Gill and Sekhri¹⁹. The limiting ionic conductances based on the above relationship are presented in Table 4.

The variation of ionic conductances with solvent composition shows that λ_o^+ values of alkali metal ions increase in the order: $\text{Li}^+ < \text{Na}^+ < \text{K}^+ < \text{Rb}^+ < \text{Cs}^+$, and for anions $\text{Br}^- < \text{Cl}^-$. The trend of variation of ionic mobilities may indicate the relative actual sizes of ions as they exist in solutions concerned²⁰. If solvation is the only effect, the sizes of these cations as they exist in solution appear to follow the order: $\text{Li}^+ > \text{Na}^+ > \text{K}^+ > \text{Rb}^+ > \text{Cs}^+$, and for anions $\text{Br}^- > \text{Cl}^-$, which indicates that Li^+ is the most solvated one and Cs^+ , the least in any mole fraction of ME.

It is thus apparent that the selective solvation of ions, the viscosity of medium, the exchange of ions with neighbouring solvent molecules, and the movement of ions through the holes in hydrogen-bond solvent system determine the variation of the Walden product with the solvent composition. However, conductance data alone are not sufficient to decide the relative importance of these factors although temperature dependence would have been a big help.

Experimental

Alkali metal chlorides and bromides (Fluka) were of purum or puriss grade and were purified as described earlier¹. Tetrabutylammonium bromide (Bu_4NBr) (Fluka, Puriss) was taken in a minimum volume of acetone. Ether was added till the commencement of precipitation. Great care was taken to ensure that ether was dry and peroxide-free. The solution was then cooled and the resulting crystals were filtered. After a preliminary drying the salt was finally

grounded and dried at 333.15 K for 48 h. Sodium tetraphenylborate (NaBPPh_4) (Fluka, Puriss) was crystallized from acetone and dried *in vacuo* at 33.15 K for 72 h.

2-Methoxyethanol (ME) (G.R., E. Merck) was dried with K_2CO_3 and distilled twice in an all-glass distillation apparatus before use. Freshly distilled ME was always used for preparing the experimental solutions. Water was first deionized and then distilled from an all-glass distilling set using alkaline KMnO_4 solution.

The solvent mixtures were prepared by weight. A stock solution for each salt ($\sim 0.1 m$) in the appropriate solvent mixture was prepared by weight and the working solutions were obtained by weight dilution. The concentration of solution was calculated from molality and density values. Densities and viscosities of solvent mixtures were measured in an Oswald-Sprengel type pycnometer and suspended-level Ubbelohde viscometer with a precision of $\pm 3 \times 10^{-5} \text{ g cm}^{-3}$ and 0.05%, respectively.

A Pye-Unicam PW 9509 conductivity meter was used for measuring the conductance of the solutions at the frequency of 2 kHz with a dip-type cell of cell constant 0.73 cm^{-1} and having an accuracy of $\pm 0.1\%$. The cell was calibrated with aqueous KCl solutions in the usual way. The measurements were carried out in a thermostated oil bath. The details of experimental procedure have been described earlier¹. Several independent solutions were prepared and runs were performed to ensure the reproducibilities of the results. All data were corrected at 298.15 K with the conductance of the solvent.

References

1. D. Nandi, S. Das and D. K. Hazra, *J. Chem. Soc., Faraday Trans. 1*, 1989, 1531.
2. L. Tassi, *J. Chem. Soc., Faraday Trans. 1*, 1993, 733.
3. P. Buckley and M. Brochu, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1972, **50**, 1149.
4. P. J. Victor, P. K. Muhuri, B. Das and D. K. Hazra, *J. Phys. Chem. (B)*, 2000, **104**, 535.
5. E. Reward and J. C. Justice, *J. Solution Chem.*, 1974, **3**, 634.
6. R. M. Fuoss, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1978, **82**, 2427.
7. R. Fernandez-Prini in "Physical Chemistry of Organic Solvent Systems", eds. A. K. Covington and T. Dickingson. Plenum, New York, 1973, Chap. 5.
8. R. L. Kay and T. L. Broadwater, *Electrochim. Acta*, 1971, **16**, 667.
9. R. L. Kay and T. L. Broadwater, *J. Solution Chem.*, 1976, **5**, 57.
10. T. L. Broadwater and R. L. Kay, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1970, **74**, 3802.
11. G. Petrella, A. Sacco, M. Castangrolo, M. Della Monica and A. Degiglio, *J. Solution Chem.*, 1977, **6**, 13.

Nandi *et al.* : Conductances of alkali metal chlorides and bromides in aqueous binary mixture *etc.*

12. G. Petrella, M. Castagnolo, A. Sacco and M. Petrella, *J. Solution Chem.*, 1980, **9**, 331.
13. G. Petrella, M. Petrella, M. Castagnolo, A. Dell'atti and A. Degiglio, *J. Solution Chem.*, 1981, **10**, 129.
14. R. Zwanzig, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1970, **52**, 3652.
15. J. B. Hubbard and R. F. Kayser, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1981, **74**, 3535.
16. M. Nakahara and K. Ibuki, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1986, **90**, 3026.
17. B. S. Krungalz, *J. Chem. Soc., Faraday Trans. 1*, 1983, 571.
18. B. S. Krungalz, *J. Chem. Soc., Faraday Trans. 1*, 1980, 1275.
19. D. S. Gill and M. B. Sekhri, *J. Chem. Soc., Faraday Trans. 1*, 1982, 119.
20. R. L. Kay and D. F. Evans, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1966, **70**, 2325.